

Some Notes on Trajan's Coinage in Alexandria¹

Sotto l'imperatore Traiano (98-117 d.C.) si assiste a un incremento significativo della produzione di dracme bronzee da parte della zecca di Alessandria d'Egitto. Parallelamente il sesterzio diviene l'emissione bronzea dominante nel sistema monetario imperiale. Sempre in quest'epoca la zecca d'Alessandria d'Egitto non è solo attiva nella emissione di monete per il sistema provinciale locale. È infatti attestato il suo coinvolgimento nella produzione di alcuni tipi di tetradrammi che circolavano in Siria. Ugualmente è noto il legame tra la zecca alessandrina e quella di Roma. Sesterzi del quinto consolato di Traiano raffiguranti l'imperatore a cavallo, all'assalto di un nemico, furono ad esempio copiati in Egitto.

L'autore sottolinea anche come non manchino nelle emissioni locali elementi che rimandano alla stessa città di Roma. Una dracma di Traiano sulla quale l'imperatore è rappresentato in trionfo mostra la raffigurazione di una colonna ed è degno di nota che tale moneta sia stata emessa poco dopo la dedicazione della colonna traiana a Roma. Raffigurazioni di edifici romani, tra i quali le terme di Traiano, appaiono anch'esse sulle monete emesse dalla zecca di Alessandria durante il regno dell'imperatore. Ciò mostra lo stretto legame tra la seconda zecca più prolifica dell'impero romano e la capitale centro del potere.

The principate of Trajan (98-117 CE) marks a watershed in the denominational composition of the coinage struck at the mint of Alexandria in Egypt. While bronze drachms were relatively rare in the first century CE, they were produced in spectacularly large quantities from Trajan onward, as has repeatedly been remarked². This shift has a close parallel in Trajan's imperial coinage, where the sestertius became the leading bronze denomination during his «COS IIII» period (101/102 CE), regarding production volume: before, the as had been the base metal denomination struck in the highest numbers³. Hence, under Trajan the transi-

tion towards larger bronze coins followed an interregional pattern. The phenomenon may be the result of economic change, and perhaps central coordination.

Michel Amandry pointed out more than forty years ago that under Trajan the mint of Alexandria in Egypt was involved in the production of tetradrachms for circulation in Syria⁴. As has become clear in the meantime through stylistic analysis, this involvement goes back to the Flavian period⁵. It continued during the short reign of Nerva (96-98 CE) and under Trajan, when Syrian tetradrachms in Egyptian style were struck with the dates «ETOYΣ NEOY IEPOY A» and «B»⁶, as well as with the Egyptian date «LIB» (year 12 = 108/109 CE)⁷. Kevin Butcher published a die-link between an Alexandria-style Syrian tetradrachm of Trajan of year 2 kept in the Dutch national collection in Amsterdam and a local Egyptian bronze hemidrachm of year 2 in the collection in Cologne⁸. This link implies that the dies for the Syrian silver coins in Egyptian style were not only cut, but also used in Alexandria under the early Trajan, and that these silver coins were clearly shipped out to Syria from Egypt. This case needs to be borne in mind for the interpretation of the Flavian issues just mentioned, which have variously been interpreted either as evidence for the shipment of dies or of coins from Egypt to Syria⁹. Several other cases of cooperation between the mints of different regions of the Roman empire have been observed for the High Principate, and there are instances in which the actual minting place is hard to ascertain¹⁰. Clearly, the shipment of ready-made coins documented for Alexandria under Trajan was often practised, but this model must not be applied indiscriminately: each case needs to be evaluated separately.

The mint of Alexandria was arguably the second most prolific mint of the Roman empire, after the capital's. There were strong ties between the two mints on various levels, as recently analysed for the Antonine period by Chris Howgego, in an important introductory chapter to *RPC IV.4*¹¹. Howgego stressed the «unparalleled closeness, for a provincial mint, of the connections between Alexandria and Rome»¹². He observed that the constant flow of information between the two mints is evident, among other things, from «the adaptation and direct copying of types from Rome» in Alexandria, but also from the creation, in Egypt, «of Roman-style types not known to have been used at Rome itself»¹³. These phenomena can be traced back to earlier periods of imperial history, and Trajan's principate provides some examples. Under Trajan the mint of Alexandria occasionally copied imperial reverses. A well-known case in point concerns Nero's (now lost) Parthian arch on the Capitoline hill¹⁴ that was prominently featured on Nero's own sestertii¹⁵. It was copied on Trajanic bronze drachms perhaps of year 13, of which just two specimens are known¹⁶. For our purpose, Alexandrian copies of original imperial Trajanic reverse types from the mint of Rome are the most interesting ones – although they are few and far between. A clear and particularly fascinating example is provided by the reverse featuring the emperor galloping to the right, thrusting a spear at an enemy kneeling underneath the horse: the foreign warrior looks

up to the emperor and begs for mercy. This reverse was first introduced into the Alexandrian type repertoire on bronze drachms in Trajan's year 11, which ran from August 107 to September 108 (fig. 1)¹⁷. Subsequently, the design was repeated perhaps in year 13, although this date is not absolutely clear on the specimens pictured in RPC, so that confirmation would be welcome (fig. 2), and eventually in year 16 (with a slight typological modification)¹⁸. As the peculiar position of the kneeling enemy on the Alexandrian coins in figs 1-2 demonstrates, the reverse is a direct copy of a Trajanic sestertius type of the «COS V» period (103-111 CE) celebrating Trajan's Dacian victories (fig. 3). I dated the prototype to «c. second half of A.D.

1. Trajan, Alexandria, drachm, year 11, RPC III, no. 4220.1, specimen no. 2: DS pl. 28, no. 728.

2. Trajan, Alexandria, drachm, year 13?, RPC III, no. 4384.1: Naville 78 (11 December 2022), lot no. 170 (35.9 mm, 21.06 g) = DS pl. 28, no. 729.

3. Trajan, Rome, sestertius, WOYTEK 2010, no. 317bC: Numismatica Ars Classica (together with Classical Numismatic Group and Numismatica Genevensis) 144 (8 May 2024: Cope coll.), lot no. 1058 (34 mm, 23.22 g).

107 to A.D. 109», on the basis of other criteria¹⁹. If this dating is correct, the type was copied in Egypt very soon after its creation at the mint of Rome.

Ten years ago, I drew attention to a rare Trajanic drachm type produced in Alexandria in year 17 (= 113/114 CE)²⁰. On the reverse, it shows a *triumphator* in his quadriga to the right, holding the customary attributes: an eagle sceptre and a laurel branch (figs. 4-5). In the background there is a column surmounted by a small statue that cannot be identified with certainty. The statue seems to raise the right hand to the head and holds an object in the left arm; in any case it clearly differs from the statue of Trajan shown atop the *columna Traiani* in imperial coin images. Still, the appearance of a column in a triumphal scene – which automatically evokes the capital, where Trajan held both of his Dacian triumphs²¹ – precisely in the year 113-114 CE is remarkable: Trajan’s column was dedicated on 12 May 113 CE²².

Column aside, the most interesting aspect of the coin image is a small figure standing behind the victorious emperor in the triumphal chariot, holding a wreath up to Trajan’s head. No wings (denoting Victoria) are in evidence, which is why I argued that this type is one of the exceedingly rare instances in which the slave reminding the triumphator of his mortality by saying the words *respice post te! hominem te memento!*²³ was depicted in Roman coinage and, indeed, Roman art in general. Since only three coins of the type were

4. Trajan, Alexandria, drachm, year 17, RPC III, no. 4798: Künker 182 (14 March 2011), lot no. 645 (26.02 g).

5. Trajan, Alexandria, drachm, year 17, RPC III, no. 4798: Heritage, Monthly Auction 271933 (18 August 2019), lot no. 35039 (33 mm, 21.53 g, 12 h).

known in 2015, of which the two museum pieces were not well preserved and one specimen in the trade (depicted here in fig. 4)²⁴ was suspected to be «somewhat tooled so the details cannot be regarded as very reliable» in RPC²⁵, this interpretation required confirmation. Fortunately, two additional drachms of the same type – both quite well preserved, and certainly not «enhanced» – have become known since:

- Alexandria, Graeco-Roman Museum, RABE – NOESKE 2016, 154, pl. 74, no. 3931 (33.7 mm, 20.50 g).
- Heritage, Monthly Auction 271933 (18 August 2019), lot no. 35039 (33 mm, 21.53 g, 12 h). Ex Classical Numismatic Auctions Ltd. 12 (26 September 1990), lot no. 71 (21.78 g) (fig. 5).

These two specimens were struck from two different pairs of dies. The coin depicted in fig. 5 is obverse die-linked to the drachm in the trade I based my interpretation on in 2015, pictured in fig. 4. More importantly, neither of the reverses of the two new coins is identical to the reverse die of the coin in fig. 4. The new specimens confirm that the figure behind the *triumphator* is wingless, and therefore it must be the *servus publicus* known from literary sources.

Another potential iconographic link with Rome in Trajan's coinage of Alexandria may be found on rare bronze drachms dated year 12 (August 108 – September 109 CE) showing on their reverse an imposing architectural structure. This type had long been regarded as depicting some triumphal or commemorative arch, possibly located in Alexandria²⁶. However, as a comparison of several specimens demonstrates, the image is accompanied by the legend «ΒΑΛΑΝΗΟΥ» in the exergue (figs. 6-7)²⁷, the genitive case of the word βαλανεῖον = (public) bath (building)²⁸. The coins show the front of an edifice with four Corinthian columns, standing on the exergual line. Crucially, no arches are in evidence between these columns²⁹, which confirms that the structure is not a triumphal *Arcus Traiani*, but a different type of building. Between the capitals of the two inner columns there is a garland, the central space between these columns is empty. Above the four columns there is a pediment featuring a globe in the centre, a symbol of Roman domination³⁰. Behind the pediment, an attic bearing a group of statues rises up. In the centre, there is a facing quadriga, with a charioteer – evidently the triumphant emperor – raising his hand in the centre. On the reverse dies featuring greater detail (compare fig. 7) the outer horses are flanked by a standing figure each. On both sides trophies (with two seated captives underneath each) complete the statuary decoration of the building. This group of statues crowning the βαλανεῖον invites comparison with statues atop other buildings on coins of the same period: for example the arch of Domitian depicted on several Alexandrian issues³¹, and two buildings of Trajan's forum in Rome, as pictured on imperial coins of the early phase of Trajan's «COS VI» period, especially the structure labelled «FORVM TRAIAN» in the exergue³². On the latter coins, Martin Beckmann convincingly identified the standing figures flanking the horses as the personifications of the helmeted Virtus (or Roma) and Honos (or the Genius populi Romani), respectively³³.

While Trajanic baths are attested for Alexandria in the literary record³⁴, the best-known baths built during his principate by far are the monumental *Thermae Traiani* in Rome. As is known from the *Fasti Ostienses*, they were dedicated and opened to the public on 22 June 109 CE³⁵ – hence precisely during Trajan’s Egyptian year 12. Unlike the grand monuments of the emperor’s forum, they were not depicted in Trajan’s imperial coinage: in fact, none of the huge bath complexes erected in the capital was ever depicted on imperial coins, evidently on the basis of a cultural choice made by the mint authorities. The authors of RPC III rightly ad-

6. Trajan, Alexandria, drachm, year 12, RPC III, no. 4287.2: Sotheby’s, 9 March 1972 (Marcel Jungfleisch coll., part II), lot no. 53.

7. Trajan, Alexandria, drachm, year 12, RPC III, no. 4287.3: C. Jackson-Jacobs coll., ex Berk 225 (30 November 2023), lot no. 507 (27.00 g).

8. Trajan, Alexandria, drachm, year 12, RPC III, no. 4317.2: Naville 33 (16 July 2017), lot no. 203 (34 mm, 23.50 g) = DS pl. 54, no. 7204 (subsequently corrected to 7224?).

mitted «the possibility» that the Alexandrian coin image is «a representation of the *Thermae Traiani* at Rome»; their statement that it may thus be «a unique representation of a building at Rome on the Alexandrian coinage of this period»³⁶ is, however, not correct: we mentioned Nero's Parthian arch on Trajanic bronze drachms minted at Alexandria, and the arch featured on Alexandrian coins of Domitian, Trajan and Hadrian that was probably located in Rome, too, as argued by Fred Kleiner³⁷.

The overall composition of the Alexandrian «BAAANHOY» reverse type of 108-109 CE – with the descriptive legend in the exergue underneath the building – reminds us of the design of the «FORVM TRAIAN» and «BASILICA VLPIA» types struck at the mint of Rome in 112-113 CE. However, examples of architectural coin types with descriptive legends in the exergue may be found already in the imperial bronze coinage of the Julio-Claudian period³⁸. In the same year 12, when Trajan's «BAAANHOY» type was produced, some Alexandrian drachms featured an elaborately decorated water basin with waterspouts in the shape of lion heads, surmounted by four columns, and three statues between them, the central one clearly representing Zeus/Jupiter. The building is crowned by the statue of an eagle, Jupiter's sacred bird (fig. 8)³⁹. This type was studied by Giovanni Maria Staffieri, who explained the structure as «una monumentale fontana-ninfeo eretta dagli alessandrini per celebrare qualche importante evento collegato alla personalità di Traiano»⁴⁰. Whether this type is to be interpreted in the context of the «BAAANHOY» coins is best left open for the time being.

BIBLIOGRAPHY

- AMANDRY 1981 = M. AMANDRY, *Un tétradrachme de type syro-phénicien frappé pour Trajan à Alexandrie*, «BNum Paris» 56, 1981, 85-87.
- BECKMANN 2005 = M. BECKMANN, *The Sculptural Group atop the Main Arch of the Forum of Trajan, in Otium. Festschrift für Volker Michael Strocka*, Th. Ganschow – M. Steinhart (eds.), Remshalden 2005, 27-32.
- BURNETT 2009 = A. BURNETT, *The Rise and Fall of the Roman "Sestertius" at Alexandria*, «SchwNumRu» 88, 2009, 225-248.
- BUTCHER 2004 = K. BUTCHER, *Coinage in Roman Syria. Northern Syria, 64 B.C.-A.D. 253*, Royal Numismatic Society Special Publication 34, London 2004.
- BUTCHER – WOYTEK 2018 = K. BUTCHER – B. WOYTEK, *The Grand Scheme of Things. Modelling Coin Production and Coin Distribution in the Roman Empire in the First and Second Centuries A.D.*, in *Infrastructure and Distribution in Ancient Economies. Proceedings of a Conference Held at the Austrian Academy of Sciences, 28-31 October 2014*, B. Woytek (ed.), Vienna 2018, 253-281.
- DS = A. SAVIO (ed.), *Numi Augg. Alexandrini. Catalogo della collezione Dattari. 380 Tavole. Introduzione supplemento e bibliografia*, second edition, Trieste 2007.
- HANDLER 1971 = S. HANDLER, *Architecture on the Roman Coins of Alexandria*, «AJA» 75, 1971, 57-74.
- KEAY – WOYTEK – MLADENOVIC 2022 = S. KEAY – B. WOYTEK – D. MLADENOVIC, *PORTVM TRAIANI. An Interdisciplinary Approach to Trajan's Harbour at Portus*, «BSR» 90, 2022, 63-107.
- KLEINER 1985 = F. S. KLEINER, *The Arch of Nero in Rome. A Study of the Roman Honorary Arch before and under Nero*, *Archaeologica* 52, Rome 1985.
- KLEINER 1989 = F. S. KLEINER, *An Arch of Domitian in Rome on the Coins of Alexandria*, «NumChron» 149, 1989, 69-81.
- McALEE 2007 = R. McALEE, *The Coins of Roman Antioch*, Lancaster 2007.
- McKENZIE 2007 = J. McKENZIE, *The Architecture of Alexandria and Egypt c. 300 B.C. to A.D. 700*, New Haven 2007.
- MILNE 1933 = J. G. MILNE, *Catalogue of Alexandrian Coins*, Oxford 1933.
- RABE – NOESKE 2016 = B. RABE – H.-C. NOESKE, *A Catalogue of the Roman Provincial Coins from the Alexandrian Mint in the Graeco-Roman Museum in Alexandria, II. The issues from Galba to Trajan (A.D. 68-117)*, Bonn 2016.
- RIC I² = C. H. V. SUTHERLAND, *The Roman Imperial Coinage, I*, second edition: *From 31 B.C. to A.D. 69*, London 1984.
- RPC II = A. BURNETT – M. AMANDRY – I. CARRADICE, *Roman Provincial Coinage, II. From Vespasian to Domitian (A.D. 69-96)*, London 1999.
- RPC III = M. AMANDRY – A. BURNETT, *Roman Provincial Coinage, III. Nerva, Trajan and Hadrian (A.D. 96-138)*, London 2015.
- RPC IV.4 = C. HOWGEGO, *Roman Provincial Coinage, IV.4. From Antoninus Pius to Commodus (A.D. 138-192). Egypt*, London 2023.
- SNG Paris = S. BAKHOUM, *Sylloge Nummorum Graecorum France, IV. Département de monnaies, médailles et antiques. Alexandrie, I. Auguste-Trajan*, Zurich 1998.
- STAFFIERI 2014 = G. M. STAFFIERI, *La «fontana di Traiano» nella monetazione alessandrina*, «NAC» 43, 2014, 255-263.
- WOYTEK 2005 = B. WOYTEK, *Zitate flavischer Reversstypen in der Münzprägung Traians*, «MÖNumGes» 45, 2005, 199-227.
- WOYTEK 2010 = B. WOYTEK, *Die Reichsprägung des Kaisers Traianus (98-117)*, *Moneta Imperii Romani* 14, Vienna 2010.
- WOYTEK 2015 = B. WOYTEK, *“Hominem te memento!” Der mahnende Sklave im römischen Triumph und seine Ikonographie*, «Tyche» 30, 2015, 193-209.

NOTES

1 I am grateful to the organisers of the Lugano symposium «Alexandria in nummis» for their kind invitation to give a paper, and to Andrew Burnett (London) for helpful comments on a draft of this contribution.

2 MILNE 1933, xxi; BURNETT 2009, 227.

3 WOYTEK 2010, 23-24.

4 AMANDRY 1981.

5 RPC II,1, 11 (Vespasian and Domitian); compare RPC II, nos. 1949 and 2402 with note 9 (tetradrachms of Vespasian often regarded as «hybrids» in scholarship, combining either an Alexandria-style obverse and a Syrian-type reverse or an Alexandrian reverse with an Alexandrian obverse featuring a legend normally reserved for dies used to strike Syrian tetradrachms in Alexandrian style). For the style of the mint of Alexandria on Syrian tetradrachms of Vespasian, see also BUTCHER 2004, 75-77, and McALEE 2007, 156-157, 166-167, no. 340.

6 RPC III, nos. 3508-3510. Compare the commentary by BUTCHER 2004, 83-84 on these issues.

7 RPC III, no. 3530.

8 RPC III, no. 4130. BUTCHER 2004, 81.

9 For the discussion, see McALEE 2007, 156-157, who opts for production in Syria with dies sent from Egypt, like the authors of RPC II; *contra* BUTCHER 2004, 77, who argues that since Vespasian all the Alexandria-style coins for Syria were probably struck in Egypt and then sent out. HowGEGO, in RPC IV.4.1, 10 follows BUTCHER 2004.

10 For an overview, see BUTCHER – WOYTEK 2018, especially 265-272.

11 RPC IV.4.1, 104-112 («Alexandria and Rome: the special relationship»).

12 RPC IV.4.1, 111.

13 RPC IV.4.1, 109.

14 The arch was either torn down af-

ter Nero's death or burnt down in one of the fires of 69 CE or 80 CE: KLEINER 1985, 94-95.

15 RIC I², Nero nos. 143-150 (Rome); 392-393 etc. (Lugdunum).

16 RPC III, no. 4455; SNG *Paris* no. 1279. KLEINER 1989, 70-71.

17 RPC III, no. 4220.1, specimen 2 = DS pl. 28, no. 728 (hitherto unique; date legible).

18 RPC III, nos. 4384 (year 13 = 109-110 CE) and 4665 (year 16 = 112-113 CE); on the latter coin, the enemy wears a Phrygian cap and is seated on the ground, not kneeling.

19 WOYTEK 2010, no. 317, with vol. 1, 128 (on dating). For the typological tradition this type stems from, see WOYTEK 2005, 212-217.

20 RPC III, no. 4798; WOYTEK 2015.

21 The dates of the two triumphs were December 102 CE and May or June 107 CE, respectively: WOYTEK 2010, 13-14.

22 *Fasti Ostienses*, tabula J, lines 54-56.

23 Tertullianus, *Apologeticus* 33.4.

24 Künker 182 (14 March 2011), lot no. 645.

25 RPC III,1, 633.

26 Thus, for example, by HANDLER 1971, 70-71. For an overview of descriptions of the structure in previous scholarship, see RPC III,1, 580.

27 RPC III, no. 4287. The legend is often hard to read or completely obliterated on the coins; it seems clearest on the specimen in fig. 6 auctioned by Sotheby's, 9 March 1972 (Marcel Jungfleisch coll., part II), lot no. 53.

28 It is not immediately obvious why the legend appears in the genitive case here. A similar puzzle is posed by an architectural coin type of Trajan from the mint of Rome, namely the sestertii featuring the emperor's new port at Ostia on the reverse, unexpectedly accompanied by the leg-

end «PORTVM TRAIANI» in the accusative case (WOYTEK 2010, no. 470): see KEAY – WOYTEK – MLADENOVIC 2022, 69-70 on this problem.

29 As correctly described by HANDLER 1971, 70: «The entablature is supported by four Corinthian columns, which seem to rise directly to it, with no indication of arches opening between them».

30 For a parallel, see the pediment of the arch of Domitian on Alexandrian coins (where the globe is held by two Victories): KLEINER 1989, 76, pl. 21.

31 For an in-depth analysis of the statuary group atop, see especially KLEINER 1989, 73-76.

32 WOYTEK 2010, nos. 403, 409 and 465.

33 BECKMANN 2005.

34 McKENZIE 2007, 250.

35 *Fasti Ostienses*, tabula J, lines 9-10: «X. K. lul. Imp. Nerva Traianus Caes. Aug. Germ. Dacicus thermas suas dedicavit et publicavit».

36 Both quotations: RPC III,1, 549.

37 KLEINER 1989.

38 RIC I² Augustus nos. 229ff. («ROM ET AVG», standing for *ara Romae et Augusti*); Tiberius nos. 80-81 («PROVIDENT», standing for *ara Providentiae*); Nero nos. 418 and 456ff. («ARA PACIS»).

39 RPC III, no. 4317.

40 STAFFIERI 2014, 258.